

**Political discontent of overeducated citizens:
The role of overeducation in political participation**

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Extended abstract

1. Context and purpose

Educational expansion in postindustrial societies has increased the supply of tertiary-educated individuals, raising concerns about mismatches between education and labor market opportunities. While some accounts emphasize an oversupply of graduates, such perspectives often overlook the dynamic nature of labor demand and the role of technological change. At the same time, labor market polarization has reduced the number of middle-skilled routine occupations (Acemoglu & Autor, 2011; Autor et al., 2003), contributing to the growing prevalence of overeducation, in which individuals' educational levels exceed job requirements (McGuinness, 2006). Overeducation may have political implications, as unmet economic and status expectations can generate discontent that extends beyond the workplace. Recent studies have documented associations between education-to-job mismatch and individual political outcomes such as ideological polarization and a sense of alienation from political life (Vaisey, 2006; Zhang, 2008; Zhu & Chen, 2016), and some pointed to indirect and context-dependent relationships driven by expectation-based mechanisms (Wiedner, 2022; Voces & Caínzos, 2022). We revisited this topic by examining the relationship between overeducation and political participation across democracies, focusing on political discontent as the explanatory mechanism and assessing how these relationships varied across contexts. We contribute to this literature by formalizing and empirically testing the discontent mechanism across European democracies, providing a theoretically grounded account of how educational mismatch translates, or fails to translate, into divergent forms of political engagement.

2. Data and methods

We defined overeducated workers as those with a tertiary education employed in occupations where the most common education level was below tertiary. Occupational education benchmarks were calculated using the 2018 EU Labour Force Survey (EU-LFS) by country, age group, and occupation (ISCO-08 two-digit). We analyzed data from the European Social Survey (ESS) Round 9, integrated with the LFS 2018 benchmarks. The mediator, political discontent, was operationalized as the inverse of political satisfaction, calculated by averaging satisfaction items for the country's democracy, economy, and government. Two forms of political participation were tested: conventional, measured by voting in national elections, and unconventional, proxied by participating in public demonstrations. To test the mechanism, we estimated a linear model and a series of generalized linear models with a logit specification appropriate for our continuous mediator, discontent, and binary participation outcomes. We controlled for country, gender, and age group, but intentionally excluded other individual characteristics, such as social origin or occupational status, since these factors may be part of the explanations by which overeducation exerts influence on participation. Adjusting for them could therefore result in downward bias in the estimated associations between overeducation and participation variables.

3. Current results and further direction

Figure 1 presents the main results, reporting average marginal estimates that quantify the average changes in predicted discontent and participation probabilities. Overeducation was positively associated with political discontent, indicating that overeducated individuals reported significantly higher levels of political discontent. Discontent then seemed to translate into distinct patterns of political participation: it was negatively associated with voting but positively associated with participation in demonstrations. In parallel, voting and demonstrating were positively correlated, suggesting that they were not mutually exclusive but reflected different forms of engagement. However, the total and direct effects of overeducation on both voting and demonstrating were null. This implied that overeducation did not directly and independently shape political behavior; instead, the association between overeducation and participation

appears to operate through political discontent rather than through a direct pathway. In addition, we observed little contextual variation, suggesting that the mechanism was relatively consistent across broader institutional settings in western democracies. Overall, our findings align with previous research and indicate that the direct political consequences of overeducation are minimal. Rather, it works behind the scenes by lowering satisfaction, which may reduce institutionalized participation and encourage more expressive forms of engagement. These findings further imply that the political consequences of educational mismatch are less about withdrawal from politics than about the forms through which individuals choose to participate. Future research should investigate differences in specific mismatch experiences across job sectors. Where feasible, longitudinal designs should also be employed to allow for more causal interpretations.

Figure 1. Estimated associations between overeducation, political discontent, and participation.

Note. Coefficients represent average marginal effects computed from linear and logit models. No total or direct effects of overeducation on participation were found, while indirect pathways operated through political discontent. Overeducation was significantly and positively associated with political discontent, which, in turn, decreased the probability of voting but increased the probability of demonstrating. Significance levels: * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$, *** $p \leq 0.001$.

Keywords: Educational mismatch, Higher education, Political discontent, Political participation

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